

Response of rainfed wetland rice to level, method, and timing of azolla application

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We conducted two azolla experiments under rainfed conditions during the 1983 crop year. The first involved two application methods (Table 1) in split-plot design with three replications. Fresh azolla was incorporated and surface-applied at 0, 10, 20, and 30 t/ha. IR36 was grown on 2- × 3-m plots at 25- × 25-cm spacing with practices suitable for rainfed culture. Partially sun-dried azolla was applied 3 d before transplanting.

The second experiment involved seven timings of azolla application (Table 2) in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Azolla was incorporated at 20 t/ha, IR36 was spaced 25 × 25 cm with 3 seedlings/ hill.

Method of application did not affect plant height, tiller count, fresh straw yield, 1000-seed weight, or the grain yield (Table 1). Taller plants occurred in all azolla-treated plots. Highest grain yield (7.0 t/ha) was with 20 t azolla/ ha.

Time of treatment did not influence height and fresh straw yield (Table 2). Azolla applied 2 WBT had the most tillers (17/hill). Applying azolla 3 WBT, 2 WBT, 1 WBT, or ATT was evidently best for grain yield; means ranged from 6.6 to 7.8 t/ha. Grain yields decreased significantly when application was after transplanting. □

Table 1. Effect of 2 application methods and 4 rates of fresh azolla on growth and yield of IR36. PSPC, Mambusao, Capiz, Philippines.

Application method	Application rate (t/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Tillers/hill (av no.)	Fresh straw wt (t/ha)	1000-seed wt (g)	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)
Surface applied	0	77.5	13	17.8	25.8	5.9
	10	87.1	15	15.2	26.4	6.7
	20	85.1	15	12.9	25.3	6.7
	30	87.0	15	14.0	27.5	6.5
Incorporated	0	81.4	13	13.7	25.8	6.5
	10	85.7	15	14.4	27.5	6.9
	20	84.4	15	15.4	26.9	7.2
	30	84.2	14	13.0	28.1	6.5
Means (rate)	0	79.4	13	15.7	25.8	6.2
	10	86.4	15	14.8	26.9	6.8
	20	84.7	15	14.2	26.1	7.0
	30	85.6	15	13.5	21.8	6.5
Means (method)	Surface applied	84.2	15	15.0	26.2	6.5
	Incorporated	83.9	14	14.1	27.1	6.8
Test of significance	Method	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
	Level	1%	ns	5%	ns	5%
	Interaction	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
LSD (for level)	5%	4.5	—	1.7	—	0.7
	1%	6.4	—	2.4	—	1.0
CV (%)	Main plot	3.6	6.6	12.8	10.0	1.3
	Sub-plot	3.0	8.5	7.2	5.6	6.1

^a Sun-dried weight.

Table 2. Time of azolla application and growth and yield components of IR36.^a PSPC, Mambusao, Capiz, Philippines.

Time of application ^b	Plant ht (cm)	Tillers (no./hill)	Fresh straw yield (t/ha)	Grain yield ^c (t/ha)
3 WBT	71.0	14 b	15.0	7.6 a
2 WBT	75.5	17 a	15.7	7.8 a
1 WBT	71.3	14 b	15.1	6.8 ab
ATT	70.0	13 b	14.9	6.6 abc
1 WT	70.7	12 b	14.7	5.6 bcd
2 WT	70.9	11 b	14.3	5.3 cd
3 WT	69.2	11 b	13.9	4.7 d
Test of significance	—	1%	—	1%
cv (%)	6.8	9.1	4.8	13.6

^a Means of 4 replications. In a column, means with a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at the 5% level. ^bWBT = weeks before transplanting, ATT = at transplanting, WT = weeks after transplanting. ^c Sun-dried weight.

Effect of Zn on yield and quality of rice in Turkey

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The effect of Zn applied with N and P on grain yield and quality of rice

grown in the main production areas of Turkey was studied. Field experiments in Central Anatolia, Çorum Province, Ankara, and at Trachia, Edirne Province, lasted 2 yr. Soil analyses of the experimental fields are shown in Table I. Seven different treatments were tested with rice variety Ribe in a randomized block design replicated four times. Treatments are in Table 2.

Urea and superphosphate were applied at 150 kg N/ha and 35 kg P/ha to all treatments.

ZnSO₄ · 7H₂O at 60 kg should be applied to the soil before seeding in Çorum; in the other states, foliar application of ZnSO₄ gave better results.

One rice quality factor is protein content. Zn had no effect on protein